

Radical translators (Britain, France and Italy, 1789–1815) through the lens of a network visualisation

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The Radical Translations (RT) - The Transfer of Revolutionary Culture between Britain, France and Italy (1789-1815) - project (Perovic et al. 2019-23), aimed to unravel the complex relationships of radical ideas during the 18th and 19th centuries, employed data models based in BIBFRAME and FOAF (King's Digital Lab 2020). By recording the information of translators - working across English, French and Italian languages - authors, publishers, and organisations involved in radical text translation, the RT project yielded valuable insights. With a quarter of the translators being anonymous, the RT project aims to bring lesser-known figures out of obscurity by mapping their social and intellectual circles.

At the time of writing, the dataset consists of 1505 agents (214 organisations - mainly publishers - and 1291 persons, of which 273 are anonymous), 237 events, and 1691 bibliographical resources (of which 947 are translations, 610 are source texts and 255 paratext records). The data model (King's Digital Lab 2020; Ciula et al. 2021) makes extensive use of values from standard vocabularies as mentioned above and controlled terms (e.g., FAST, Wikidata, VIAF, GeoNames, EDTF) for general data classification, for subjects and topics, for person names, for place names, and for dates. Project-specific classification schemes were also adopted drawing on terminology from the literature (e.g. with respect to the status of each translation as integral, partial, abridged, etc. and with respect to forms of paratext: titlepages, dedications, epigraphs, prefaces, addenda, notes, etc.). This granularity was introduced during the data collection process to grasp the variety of “18th-century translation practices”, inclusive of “published translations (whole or partial), retranslations, indirect translations, texts presented as translations, and self-translations [... but also] also [...] projected, but unrealised or unpublished translations, announced, for instance, in short-lived periodicals or publisher's prospectuses” (Mucignat and Perovic 2023).

Similarly, to capture aspects of social, professional and political identity of activists, biographical information about translators include their contributing roles e.g. as translators, authors, publishers or journalists, as well as static attributes (dates, places of birth) and acquired or life-attributes (languages spoken, date of death, main place of residence and other important places of residences, the organisations to which they belonged, and the people they knew) (Mucignat and Perovic 2023).

This submission highlights the implementation of graph network methodologies, specifically focusing on the agents' (people, organisations) networks visualisations. Using biographical and bibliographical data, the visualisation implemented on the Observable platform⁶⁵ represents people (authors, translators, publishers) and organisations within the translation network. The graph edges signify relationships such as being based in a place, editorial connections, interpersonal relationships (knows), organisational memberships (member of), publication relationships (published), publication in a specific place, and translation relationships (translated).

The network geometry inherently abstracts complex personal trajectories into nodes and edges, offering a comprehensive yet simplified perspective. Although the visualisations are inherently incomplete and subject to change with ongoing data updates, they have proven indispensable in the iterative research process (Mucignat and Perovic 2023). The networks serve both descriptive and argumentative purposes, guiding the research by highlighting potential gaps, omissions, and biases in the data. For example, recording and examining the contextual information about cultural and political organisations (e.g. “networks of sociability” such as radical circles, printers, publishers, newspapers) to which translators belonged as well as the recurring places as “contact zones”(from key cities such as Milan, Paris and London to border areas, such as Oneglia and the Liguria region, and provincial towns, such as Newcastle and Norwich) has informed an alternative strategy to de-anonymisation tout-court. It deals with a process of drawing the contours around social, professional and political identities by bringing to the fore complementary “circumstantial evidence”. Despite the limitations of the selection of agents in the data source and the “blunt instrument” of the ‘knows’ property in the FOAF model, the network also makes emerge the connections of “political solidarity” enabled by translation “across linguistic and national borders, even in times of war or political repression” (Mucignat and Perovic 2023). Finally, given the data collection on biographies was very limited in terms of time-indicators, the exploration of the networks complemented this gap offering visual traces to test hypothesis around people's movements and life stories.

By integrating graph networks into the research framework, this submission highlights the expanded dimensions of inquiry within the RT project. The visualisations enable an exploration of translators' networks, revealing collaboration patterns, influence dynamics, and the contextual landscape of radical activities during the period under study. This contribution aims to present the network visualisation design and build methods (Smithies and Ciula 2020; Ciula et al. 2023) as well as its role as a powerful tool for hypothesis verification offering insights into the intricate connections shaping history.

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